

THE NEGATIVE EFFECT OF POPULATION MIGRATION ON THE FAMILY ENVIRONMENT

Dilshoda Turgunbayeva

Andijan State University Geography (on the object of study) specialty Master's student Andijan,
Uzbekistan

dilshodaturgunboyeva0109@gmail.com

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Abstract. *Human migration is one of the specific phenomena of the era of globalization, and today we can observe its negative impact on the changes in the system of family relations, the moral essence of the family. It is known that the types of migration are extensive and its features have been discussed in detail. The article highlights the negative impact of migration on the socio-ethical environment of the family, the system of moral values. The author emphasizes that due to migration, the number of divorces in Uzbek families is growing, the upbringing of children is becoming more complicated, and family traditions are changing.*

Keywords: *state, person, international organization, international migration, family, population migration, migrant, moral environment in the family, child upbringing, family values.*

Introduction

Ethical values reflect the moral essence of a person and society, and their stability and the fact that they are based on universal moral principles are necessary for the development of the moral environment. Usually, when we say moral values, every person, nation, nation, nation is relatively stable, acquires stability, expresses and manifests its identity in economic, political, legal, spiritual-cultural, daily household activities and is highly valued. , highly developed moral qualities and virtues (such as humanity, justice, legality, patriotism, politeness, honesty) are meant. In other words, the basic concepts of morality, moral principles and moral standards together form a system of moral values. The stability of this system, the ability to combine universality and nationalism at the same time is the spiritual development of society and has a positive effect on national growth. The part of the system of moral values related to the institution of the family constitutes the family moral values, which reflect the social and moral ideals, ideas, principles, and norms valued by every family and corresponding to the criteria of both universal and national morality.

The family value system affects the stability of the moral environment of the whole society. In the family, the child is inculcated with moral and educational values, such as proper greetings, dressing, interaction with adults and peers, and behavior in public. When a child takes a step towards self-awareness, he begins to get to know his surroundings, relatives, parents who care for him, and to imitate and master their behavior. Qualities such as hard work, loyalty, sincerity, trust, love of country, justice, purity, correctness, which are characteristic of Uzbek families, are directly instilled from parents to children as a personal example. Our sons and daughters, who enjoy our traditions and culture, are instilled with the feeling of helping their parents and caring for their families from a young age. The family, as a guarantee of the stability of the moral environment in the society, faces ideological, ideological, and moral threats of various forms and contents in the era of globalization. One of the factors negatively affecting the stable moral environment of the family institution is the phenomenon of population migration.

Materials and methods

The fact that population migration in Uzbekistan affects the transformational processes in the socio-ethical environment, the system of moral values, the appearance of immoral and harmful threats in the life of our society, the emergence of "mass culture" that contradicts our national moral values we can observe in such processes as the introduction of various forms, changes in the system of family relations, the national moral image and essence of the family, the attitude towards its sanctity is changing, the introduction of new values for our society in conducting weddings and family ceremonies.

The direct impact of the processes of migration and return migration (that is, the return of migrants from the country of immigration to their homeland) on the system of moral values in our country, and the resulting changes in the moral environment, can be divided into two parts:

1) positive changes taking place in the moral environment of our society due to migration, in particular, universal moral values, interethnic harmony, interreligious tolerance, the establishment of the ethics of tolerance at all levels of social relations, moral responsibility in society towards migrants and their families being formed;

2) the negative impact of migration on the stability of the ethosphere of our society, in particular, the increased threat of terrorism, extremism and similar destructive ideologies due to migration, various manifestations of "popular culture", the promotion of immorality, the devaluation of our national moral values, the family the moral essence and image of the institution is undergoing transformation, deformation, incomplete families, increasing divorces, etc.

The negative effects of population migration on the social and moral environment of our country are felt more than the positive effects. One of the main reasons for this is that migrants and emigrants who have recently returned to their homeland are outside the influence of social control institutions such as family, neighborhood, educational institutions, which protect them from various threats and immoral forms of the state and society in the receiving country. This can lead to young people traveling abroad as migrants falling under the influence of various harmful vices and destructive organizations. The fact that immigrants, whose individual moral values have been deformed in various ways, constantly communicate with their relatives, family members, peers or return to Uzbekistan cannot but negatively affect the stability of the moral environment. One of the significant negative effects of population migration on the ethosphere in our country is the transformation of the moral image of the family institution in our society, changes in the system of family relations, an increase in the number of divorces, the emergence of single-parent families, and moral problems in child rearing. One of the main problems that our compatriots abroad, especially labor migrants, face after returning to Uzbekistan is the deterioration of relations between husband and wife and relatives in family life, and the crisis of family moral environment due to insufficient attention to children. One of the main reasons for this is that ex-migrants who have adapted to the criteria of a different moral environment have difficulty re-accepting family moral criteria, and their views on life with family members begin to differ. Life ideals of people who have not lived together for a long time are far from each other. These problems in the relationship can lead to family quarrels, even divorce, and children become living orphans. This has a negative impact on the stability of the family moral environment and thereby the stability of the moral environment in the whole society. Another negative effect of population migration on family morals is manifested in the upbringing of children. Usually, the majority of migrants are people aged 20-40, most of them (two-thirds) are married and have minor children. In most cases, migrants do not take their families and children abroad.

Results and its discussion

The fact that the father or the mother or both of them are away from the children in the family leads to a change in the system of moral values in the family. In particular, the role of the father in raising children in the family is incomparable. According to statistics, 81% of labor migrants who returned to our country in 2017 were men and 19% were women. While the male migrant is abroad, his family becomes a temporary incomplete family, which causes problems in the upbringing of children whose fathers are far away, and even the children of migrants may become morally depressed. Social studies conducted by UNICEF, the United Nations Children's Fund, show that approximately 33% of children from our country, whose parents are abroad, feel unhappy, and 21% are constantly lives in worry. This has a negative impact on the mental and moral development of children, and can cause them to develop deviant behavior and various moral vices. 8% of such children do not follow the order and moral rules established in society, 6% fight, 18% are rude to adults, and 37% behave in this way to their peers. In some cases, children of migrants are subjected to mental and physical pressure. This can affect children's psyche, cause stress and depression, and sometimes this situation can cause children to intentionally harm themselves. Sometimes migrant workers can take their children abroad with them. In this case, the children of migrants abroad fall into the trap of various forms of "mass culture", ideas and ideologies that are contrary to our national mentality, and destructive behavior is formed in them. Even after the return of the children of migrants, due to the formation of customs, traditions, and values specific to the culture of other peoples and nations from a young age, they have problems in accepting national values and traditions, in establishing relations with relatives they have not dealt with or seen for a long time, peers. he may face difficulties in regaining his place in his circle and finding his reputation, he may associate his future prospects with the foreign country where he lived. This makes it difficult for children to find their place in society and causes moral and psychological depression. Due to migration, it is difficult for children who have the above problems to grow up to be mature and moral individuals. In particular, the highest moral qualities of a person that should be formed in the family are considered to be humility, courage, kindness, discipline, thrift, gentleness, generosity, generosity, correctness, imagination, diligence, and loyalty, and they are also considered when the children of migrants become adults. may not be fully formed. All this is a negative consequence of the phenomenon of population migration in relation to the moral environment in the family. It should be noted that the family as a value has always been the central link of the system of moral values of our society. A change in attitude towards it, a transformation of the mental and moral content of the family, and the fact that it is not valued as before can lead to a change in the system of moral values for our entire society, or even a decline. As the number of migrants in the society increases, a generation is formed that is far from the traditional moral relations between parents and children in a traditional family, and family values. As one of the main social tasks of the family is to raise a highly moral generation of the society, it becomes difficult for the family, which is in disarray due to migration, to fulfill this task. This has a negative impact on the stability of the moral environment of our society and the system of moral values.

Conclusions

In conclusion, we can say that the stability of the moral environment in our country, the priority of universal and national moral values in social life is an important factor in the general development of the society's spirituality. Due to the phenomenon of population migration, the transformation and evolution of the socio-ethical environment and the system of moral values, unfortunately, shows negative consequences. Along with such negative consequences, we can

show that the crisis of family morals, difficulties in raising children, the increased risk of threats to our security and peace, many immoralities enter the life of Uzbek families under the guise of "popular culture".

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